

ISic0184

I.Sicily inscription 0184

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found in excavations in Piazza Duomo in mid-March 1878

Coordinates

37.987048, 13.696422

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 2

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 17 cm

Width 34.5 cm

Depth 7.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ianuarius

2. ser(vus) vix(it) an(nis) XIIX

3. Successa filio pio

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini

Translation (en)

Ianuarius, slave, lived for 18 years. Successa (set this up) for her dutiful son

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285225

EDR 127389

EDCS 22100115

Bibliography

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